

Formulation And Evaluation of Chitosan-Based Hydrogel Incorporating *Musa Paradisiaca* and *Curcuma Longa* for Acute Wound Healing

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ABSTRACT

Inflammatory response, cell proliferation, collagen synthesis and tissue modeling are all involved in the complex biological event taking place during wound healing. A perfect wound dressing, which retains moisture in the wound bed, protects from microorganisms, and stimulates tissue regeneration is required for the treatment of acute wounds. For the generation and evaluation of a natural and biocompatible wound healing dressing for acute wounds, this study was aimed to develop and evaluate chitosan-based hydrogel supplemented with *Musa paradisiaca* and *Curcuma longa* extracts. The hydrogel was fabricated by the freeze-thaw technique through dissolving chitosan in a mild solvent at acetic acid glacial. Chitosan and herbal extract solutions were prepared in different concentrations to obtain three different formulations (F1, F2, and F3). The physical appearance profile of the prepared hydrogels such as clarity, pH, homogeneity, spreadability viscosity and drug content uniformity was determined. Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was employed in the in vitro diffusion study to determine the release profile of the active compounds. Biocompatibility and cytotoxicity were determined using Vero cell lines with an MTT-assay, wound healing ability assessed by in-vitro scratch assay. Formulation F3 showed superior physicochemical properties, extended drug release and high cell survival when compared to the other two formulations. Scratch wound assay revealed significant increase in cell motility and remarkable closure of the wound between F3 and other formulations. Results Chitosan in combination with *Musa paradisiaca* and *Curcuma longa* extracts was effective in promoting acute wound healing. Overall, the optimized chitosan herbal hydrogel can be considered as an alternative safe, cost-effective and prospective candidate for healing of acute wounds

Keywords: Hydrogel, Chitosan, *Musa paradisiaca*, *Curcuma longa*, Freeze thaw method, Acute wound healing.

INTRODUCTION

Healing of wounds is a process that comprises inflammatory response, cellular proliferation, collagen deposit and tissue remodelling, which takes place in the body. A dressing has to maintain the wound moist, cover the exposure from germs and assist in tissue formation. A Hydrogel is known to be especially suitable for these purposes, due to their hydrophilic 3D network structure, high water absorption capacity, elasticity and biocompatibility. Their ability to keep a moistened environment and

assist in drug delivery is significant for managing acute wounds.

The acute wound covers are held in a moist environment for faster regeneration of tissue, enabling the skin to heal. They act as a protective layer against global pollutants and are free of latex and fibreglass. They also reduce pain and trauma during dressing changes, and absorb excess exudate.

Chitosan is a natural polysaccharide derived from chitin. It is usually incorporated in hydrogel systems

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its biodegradable, non-toxic, an antimicrobial activity and a promising wound healing effect. It stimulates fibroblast growth, has a haemostatic effect and increases collagen synthesis. Incorporation of therapeutic plant bioactive compounds into chitosan hydrogels can enhance their efficiency.

Musa paradisiaca is traditionally used for wound healing, burns and skin inflammation. The high concentration levels of flavonoids, polyphenols & antioxidants in Propolis can alleviate oxidative stress and promote tissue repair. *Curcuma longa* containing curcuminoids including curcumin has a strong anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant activity that favours wound healing. Together, these two herbal extracts may have beneficial additive effects on the healing of cutaneous wounds.

In the present research work, a chitosan hydrogel loaded with *Musa paradisiaca* and *Curcuma longa* extracts was formulated for use as a natural biocompatible wound dressing material. The dissolving solution was prepared with glacial acetic acid, which is a mild and skin compatible solvent for the dissolution of chitosan compared to harsh acids. The freeze-thaw method was used to obtain efficient crosslink and stable hydrogel. In general, incorporation of the herbal extracts into a chitosan hydrogel matrix could be considered as a potential, cost-effective and safe approach to accelerate acute wound healing without compromising ideal wound management.

AIM:

To formulate and evaluate a chitosan-based hydrogel formulation for acute wound healing by incorporating *Musa paradisiaca* and *Curcuma longa*.

OBJECTIVES: ^[5] ^[20]

- ❖ To formulate a *Curcuma longa* and *Musa paradisiaca* aqueous extract containing chitosan-based hydrogel for acute wound.
- ❖ In order to evaluate the pH, transparency, homogeneity, viscosity and spreadability of hydrogels as well as other physicochemical properties.

- ❖ For in vitro diffusion profile and content uniformity of drug.
- ❖ To study its cytotoxicity and biocompatibility of the structure in vitro using cell lines.
- ❖ Test the formulations' ability to close wound by scratch wound assay.
- ❖ The identification of an optimal hydrogel which promotes faster healing in the acute wounds from different formulations was assessed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: ^[6] ^[12] ^[19] ^[7]

MATERIALS: Fresh leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* & *Curcuma longa* rhizomes were collected from the local vendors of Kanchipuram district of Tamil Nadu. It was authenticated by Botanist Dr. KN Sunil Kumar of Siddha Central Research Institute, Arumbakkam, Chennai (Code No:M04092501P, C04092502L).

The following reagents used were domestic and of analytical grade Chitosan, Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), glacial acetic acid, ethanol, distilled water.

EXTRACTION OF MUSA PARADISIACA: The collected leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* were cleaned, chopped into small pieces, air-dried in shade, and mechanically ground into fine powder filtered through a 60# mesh. 50g of the powder were extracted using a Soxhlet apparatus with 99% ethanol (1:5 w/v) for 12 hours at 72°C. the extract was concentrated and stored in amber-coloured glass bottle at 4°C.

EXTRACTION OF CURCUMA LONGA: The collected rhizomes of *curcuma longa* were cleaned, chopped into small pieces, air-dried in shade, and mechanically ground into fine powder filtered through a 60# mesh. 50g of the powder were extracted using a Soxhlet apparatus with 99% ethanol (1:5 w/v) for 12 hours at 57°C. the extract was concentrated and stored in amber-coloured glass bottle at 4°C.

PLANT PROFILE: ^[9]

VERNACULAR NAMES - *MUSA PARADISIACA*:

Table 01: Vernacular names of *Musa paradisiaca*

English	Banana leaf
Tamil	Vazhai
Telugu	Arati, Kadamu
Malayalam	Vazha, Kadalivala
Kannada	Baale Hannu
Hindi	Kela, Kadali
Marathi	Kela, Kadaan

Figure 01: *Musa paradisiaca***TAXONOMICAL CLASIFICATION - *MUSA PARADISIACA*:****Table 02: Taxonomical classification of *Musa paradisiaca***

Kingdom	Plantae
Phylum	Tracheophytes
Subphylum	Angiosperms
Class	Monocots
Order	Zingiberales
Family	Musaceae
Genus	Musa
Species	M. Paradisiaca

VERNACULAR NAMES - *CURCUMA LONGA*:**Table 05: Phytochemical Screening of plant extracts**

S.No.	Identification test	Observation	Inference
1.	Alkaloids a. Mayer's Test Test extract + Mayer's reagent b. Tannic acid Test Test extract + Tannic acid solution	Cream coloured precipitate Buff coloured precipitate	Presence of alkaloids Presence of alkaloids

Table 03: Vernacular names of *Curcuma longa*

English	Turmeric, Indian Saffron
Tamil	Manjal
Telugu	Haridra
Malayalam	Manjal
Kannada	Arishina
Hindi	Haldi
Marathi	Halad

Figure 02: *Curcuma longa***TAXONOMICAL CLASIFICATION-*CURCUMA LONGA*:****Table 04: Taxonomical classification of *Musa paradisiaca***

Kingdom	Plantae
Phylum	Tracheophytes
Subphylum	Angiosperms
Class	Monocots
Order	Zingiberales
Family	Zingiberaceae
Genus	Musa
Species	M. Paradisiaca

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING: ^[10]

2.	<p>Glycosides</p> <p>a. Extract +5ml dil.H₂SO₄, heat on water bath, neutralize with 5% NaOH solution,0.1ml Fehling's A and B until it becomes alkaline, heat on water bath for 2 minutes.</p> <p>b. Extract +5ml water, heat on water bath, 5% NaOH solution,0.1ml Fehling's A and B until it becomes alkaline, heat on water bath for 2 minutes.</p>	<p>Red precipitate</p> <p>Red precipitate</p>	<p>Presence of Glycosides</p> <p>Presence of Glycosides</p>
3.	<p>Tannins</p> <p>a. Gelatin Test Test solution + Gelatin solution containing 10%NaCl</p> <p>b. Lead acetate Test Alcoholic extract + Lead acetate Solution.</p>	<p>Precipitate is formed</p> <p>White precipitate</p>	<p>Presence of Tannins</p> <p>Presence of Tannins</p>
4.	<p>Carbohydrates</p> <p>a. Molisch's Test Extract + Molisch's reagent, shake and add Conc.H₂SO₄from sides of test tube.</p> <p>b. Fehling's Test Extract + Fehling's Solution A and B reagents</p>	<p>Formation of Violet colour ring at junction of 2 liquids.</p> <p>Brick red precipitate</p>	<p>Presence of Carbohydrates</p> <p>Presence of Carbohydrates</p>
5.	<p>Flavonoids</p> <p>a. NaOH test Extract + NaOH Solution</p> <p>b. Lead acetate Test Extract + Lead acetate solution</p>	<p>Coloured precipitate</p> <p>Yellow coloured precipitate</p>	<p>Presence of Flavonoids</p> <p>Presence of Flavonoids</p>
6.	<p>Amino acids</p> <p>a. Ninhydrin test Extract + Ninhydrin Solution and boil.</p> <p>b. Millon's test Extract + Millon's reagent</p>	<p>Purple colour</p> <p>White precipitate</p>	<p>Presence of Amino acids</p> <p>Presence of Amino acids</p>
7.	<p>Proteins</p> <p>a. Coagulation Test Heat the Test solution in a water bath</p>	<p>Coagulation occurs</p>	<p>Presence of Proteins</p>

	b. Lead acetate Test Test solution + 40%NaOH + 10%lead acetate Solution.	Brown precipitate	Presence of Proteins
8.	Phytosterols and Triterpenoids a. Salkowski Test Extract + Chloroform +Conc.H ₂ SO ₄ , Shake well. b. Sulphur Test Test solution + sulphur Powder.	Red coloured CHCl ₃ layer Yellow coloured CHCl ₃ layer Sinks at the bottom	Presence of Steroids Presence of Triterpenoids Presence of Triterpenoids
9.	Terpenoids Test for Volatile Oils a. Extract placed on filter paper b. Extract + Alcohol Test for Resins a. Heat the extract b. Burn the extract	Filter paper is permanently stained. Soluble Softens and melts Smoky flame is produced	Presence of Volatile Oils Presence of Volatile Oils Presence of Resins Presence of Resins
10.	Fixed oils and Fats a. Extract pressed between two filter papers b. Extract + Alcohol	Filter paper is permanently stained. Insoluble	Presence of Fixed oils Presence of Fixed oils
11.	Gums and Mucilage a. Test solution + Ruthenium red solution b. Powdered drug + water	Pink colour Particles swell	Presence of Gums and Mucilage Presence of Gums and Mucilage

PRE-FORMULATION STUDIES: ^[15] ^[17] ^[13]

i. FOURIER TRANSFORM INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (FTIR)

Its functional groups of drugs were confirmed by Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR). The sample was crushed and mixed with potassium bromide and compressed to form a pellet. This pellet was then scanned in the range of wavenumbers from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ with a speed of 4 mm/s and spectral

resolution of 2 cm⁻¹. The obtained spectra were analyzed to assign the principal absorption bands.

ii. UV-VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY (UV)

UV-visible Spectrophotometer measurements were used to determine the absorption profile of drug. For appropriate dilution, weighed sample amount was dissolved in a suitable solvent. The absorbance of the resulting solution was

scanned in the wavelength range of 200 to 400 nm by a UV-Vis spectrophotometer and its solvent served as blank for baseline correction. Finally, Absorbance spectrum was measured to determine the λ_{max} .

iii. THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY (TLC):

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) Silica gel pre-coated plates were used for TLC. Plant extracts were spotted on the plates with capillary tubes and spots were indicated by small dotted lines. Thereafter, only one

mobile phase was employed for plate development. After development the plates were air dried and examined under UV light to check for quenched areas or lumione. The bands were subsequently exposed to iodine vapours to develop the bands more clearly. The mobility of each constituent was tested according to its retention factor (Rf) and Rf values were determined for all fractions. The positions of each spot observed on the TLC plates were noted and taken for analysis after drying and visualisation under UV light and iodine fumes.

Distance travelled by solute

$$R_f = \frac{\text{Distance travelled by solute}}{\text{Distance travelled by solvent}} \times 100$$

FORMULATION: [13] [10]

Table 06: Formulation table for hydrogel

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
1.	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	0.5g	1g	1.5g
2.	Curcuma longa	0.5g	1g	1.5g
3.	Chitosan	0.5g	1g	1.5g
4.	Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose	10ml	10ml	10ml
5.	Poly vinyl alcohol	10ml	10ml	10ml
6.	Glacial acetic acid	0.10ml	0.10ml	0.10ml
7.	Distilled water (makeup)	50ml	50ml	50ml

PROCEDURE:

- **STEP-1:**
 - ✓ Take a 1% glacial acetic acid dissolving in 100 mL of distilled water, then take 30 mL of above solution. Add chitosan. Stir at 60-80°C for 1.5 hrs until the solution becomes homegenous.
- **STEP-2:**
 - ✓ 0.1g of sodium carboxy methyl cellulose was dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water. The solution was prepared at a temperature of 50 ± 5 °C with constant stirring until a homogeneous mixture was obtained.
- **STEP-3:**
 - ✓ 0.5 g of poly vinyl alcohol was dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water. The solution was prepared at a temperature of 75 ± 5 °C with constant stirring until a homogeneous mixture was obtained.
- **STEP-4:**
 - ✓ The sodium carboxy methyl cellulose solution was then slowly added to the chitosan solution under continuous stirring, followed by the gradual addition of the PVA solution. Finally, the *Musa paradisiaca* and *Curcuma longa* extracts were incorporated into the mixture, and stir the solution until a homogeneous formulation was obtained.
- **STEP-5:**
 - ✓ Pour into petriplate in (90mm).

- ✓ Freeze at 4°C for 12 hrs, thaw at 25 ± 3 for 6 hrs, repeated 5-7 cycle.

- **STEP-6:**

Transfer hydrogel into air-tight container; stored at 8°C in refrigerator.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS: ^[16]^[19]^[20]^[5]

I. CLARITY:

The clarity of each formulation was visually examined over black-and-white background and scored on the basis of turbid, clear or obvious.

II. pH:

2.5 g of hydrogel was accurately weighed and dissolved in 25 ml of distilled water. The pH of the mixture was measured with a digital pH meter.

III. HOMOGENEITY:

All made hydrogels were observed visually on their appearance and aggregates in the container.

IV. SPREADABILITY:

Spreadability Spreading diameter was measured as mentioned by 0.5 g of hydrogel formulation sandwiched between two-horizontal smooth surfaces of glass plates (20 cm x 20 cm). The hydrogel was positioned on the glass plate and its initial diameters in cm were measured. The hydrogel was placed under another 200 g of glass (of the same size) for one minute or until the hydrogel ceased to expand. The circle that was created after hydrogel spreading and drying was measured in centimeters with the upper plate slowly taken off.

V. VISCOSITY:

Viscosities of the hydrogel were determined by a viscometer (Brookfield DV-II). The rotational speed of the spindle was 100 rpm. The hydrogel samples were allowed to settle for 30 min prior to taking measurements. Calculations were done in the three sample average.

VI. DRUG CONTENT:

After weighed amount of hydrogel (1 g) was introduced, the volumetric flask with 50 ml of phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.4) was finally made up to the volume with phosphate buffer. Volumetric flask containing warfarin-laden hydrogel was sonicated for 15 min to get complete solubilization of drug. The mixture was filtered through a 0.45 m membrane filter. The absorbance of the resulting solution was recorded at λ max: 277.4 nm against phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as blank on ultraviolet (UV)/visible spectrophotometer.

VII. TIME FOR DRYING:

A drying time of the films was taken after application of gels. 1 g of the hydrogel was cast on glass slide. The time required for the complete drying of hydrogel into a film was noted down. To ensure thorough drying of the films, a second cover glass was lightly forced on to them. The film was considered as dry if no visible hydrogel remained on the glass slide after peel off.

VIII. IN VITRO DIFFUSION STUDY:

An egg membrane cleaned and placed in the diffusion media for 1 day was mounted over a donor compartment to which 1 g of formulation had been applied. The donor compartment is placed in the receptor compartment containing 400 ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. The beaker of the receptor compartment, which contained the diffusion medium is kept at 37 degrees C throughout exposure and stirred continuously at 22 rpm by a magnetic stirrer. 5 ml samples are withdrawn from the diffusion medium at hourly intervals for 12 hrs and replaced with an equal volume of fresh, pre-warmed diffusion medium. Spectrophotometer The samples were evaluated for papain spectrophotometrically at 277.4 nm using Shimadzu double-beam UV-visible spectrophotometer. All the just formulations were subjected to a diffusion study and kinetic models and statistical analysis was performed to compare release patterns.

Table 07: Parameters for In-Vitro Diffusion Study

Parameters	Hydrogel
Diffusion medium	Phosphate buffer pH 7.4
Volume	400 ml
Rpm	22
Temperature	37° C □ 1° C
UV Absorbance Measurement	277.4 nm

IX. MTT Assay:

In vitro cytotoxicity of the formulation against Vero cells was evaluated by MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay. Vero cells harvested with trypsinisation were centrifuged, adjusted and then seeded at a final density of 1×10^3 cells/mL (200 μ L/well) into the wells of a 96-well tissue culture plate using DMEM supplemented with 1% FBS and 1% solution of antibiotic. The cells were incubated at 37°C for 24-48 h. After incubation was finished, the glasses were washed with aseptic PBS and then treated to different formulation concentration in DMEM without serum. After 24 h of incubation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂, the treatment assays were performed for triplicate. After the addition of 20 μ L MTT solution (5 mg/mL) to each well, cells were incubated for an additional two or four hours until purple formazan crystals became visible as observed with the inverted microscope. The wells were then rinsed with 200 μ L of $1 \times$ PBS and 100 μ L DMSO was added for formazan crystal dissolution, after removing the MTT-containing media (220 μ L). Absorbance was read at 570 nm by a microplate reader (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) after shaking the plate for five min. IC₅₀ values and percentage cell viability were determined by GraphPad Prism 6.0 software (USA).

X. SCRATCH WOUND ASSAY:

Living cells, need to move otherwise they would not be of any help for immunological defense, proper growth and the pathology processes such as

inflammation and spreading of cancer. Methods to study cell migration are essential and useful in a variety of biomedically relevant areas, including cancer biology, immunology, vascular biology, cell biology and developmental biology.

Materials: DMEM, Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS), and antibiotic solution were procured from Gibco (USA) and 1X PBS was purchased from Himedia (India). Wash beaker and six-well tissue culture plate were purchased from Tarson (India).

Methodology:

Migration of cancer and non-cancer cells after treatment was measured by a wound healing test. Vero cells were seeded in six-well tissue culture dishes and allowed to grow to 90% confluence in full media. As reported, a 2 mm plastic point which touched the plate destroyed the monolayers of cells. After 4 medium washes to remove cell debris, wounded monolayers were incubated in 1% FBS media. The cells were then incubated for 24 h after the

administration of 130 µg/ml of formulation. The cells were observed with a camera using an inverted microscope. The wound sizes were analyzed with Image-J software (NIH, Bethesda, MD). The wound area ratio was calculated with the wound area of the control and treated sample.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

I. PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING:

It has been confirmed that the leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* and *curcuma longa* rhizomes contain various phytochemical constituents. Therefore, it is important to establish a standard to maintain their quality. The extracts were subjected to preliminary phytochemical analysis to detect the various phytochemical constituents. The analysis exposed the presence of flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, and other compounds.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis of *Musa paradisiaca* leaves and *curcuma longa* rhizomes extract:

Table 08: Phytochemical screening of plant extracts

(+) Presence (-) Absence

S. No.	Test	Ethanollic extract of <i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Ethanollic extract of <i>Curcuma longa</i>
1.	Alkaloids	+	+
2.	Glycosides	+	+
3.	Tannins	+	+
4.	Carbohydrates	+	+
5.	Flavonoids	+	+
6.	Amino acids	+	+
7.	Proteins	-	+
8.	Phytosterols and Triterpenoids	-	+
9.	Terpenoids	+	-
10.	Fats and oils	-	-
11.	Gums & Mucilage	-	-

II. FTIR For *Musa paradisiaca*:

The FTIR spectra of *Musa paradisiaca* showed a broad absorption band at 3371.30 cm^{-1} due to the stretching vibrational band of hydroxyl (O–H) groups. Two bands at 2922.51 cm^{-1} and 2853.13 cm^{-1} are corresponding to the aliphatic C–H

stretching. A carbonyl group is shown by the absorption band at 1738.60 cm^{-1} , for C=O stretching. The peaks at 1450.50 and 1377.29 cm^{-1} are C–H bending, whilst aromatic C=C stretching which is observed in the region of 1514.13 cm^{-1} . Alcohols or ethers are identified by the strong absorption band at 1035.67 cm^{-1} due to C–O stretching bond.

Figure 03: FTIR of *Musa paradisiaca* leaves extract

III. FTIR For *Curcuma longa*:

The FTIR spectra of *Curcuma longa* showed a broad O–H stretching band at 3330.24 cm^{-1} , characteristic C–H stretching vibrations at 2925.05 cm^{-1} . A peak at 1622.58 cm^{-1} is due to C=O, or aromatic C=C stretching. Aromatic and aliphatic bending vibrations are established by 1509.72 cm^{-1} , 1429.80 cm^{-1} and 1377.22 cm^{-1}

peak(s). Strong C–O stretching bands were observed at 1163.20 cm^{-1} , 1126.16 cm^{-1} , and 1030.42 cm^{-1} .

Figure 04: FTIR of *Curcuma longa* extract

IV. FTIR For Chitosan:

The hydroxyl and amine functional groups in chitosan and phytoconstituents were confirmed by the strong absorption band at 3451.18 cm^{-1} in the FTIR spectrum, corresponding to O–H and N–H stretching vibration (Fagbohun et al., 2019). The characteristic peaks at 2920.05 cm^{-1} and 2867.35 cm^{-1} were attributed to aliphatic C–H stretching vibrations. The weak peak at 2144.00 cm^{-1} can be ascribed to the C=C–H stretching of unsaturated functional groups. The amide I (C=O stretching) of chitosan is indicated by the strong

absorption band at 1651.88 cm^{-1} , and amide II (N–H bending) represented as a band at 1592.13 cm^{-1} . The maxima at 1383.11 cm^{-1} and 1326.18 cm^{-1} are attributed to the C–H bending and C–N stretching vibrations, respectively. The strong peaks at 1153.66 cm^{-1} and 1032.92 cm^{-1} are attributed to C–O–C and C–O stretching vibrations, indicating the presence of polysaccharide structure, which is also supported by a peak observed at 1260.38 cm^{-1} corresponding to C–O stretching. The peaks were situated at 893.40 cm^{-1} , 665.94 cm^{-1} and 605.75 cm^{-1} respectively.

Figure 05: FTIR of Chitosan

V. UV For Musa paradisiaca:

Figure 06: UV of Musa paradisiaca

TABLE 09: UV absorbance *curcuma longa* in phosphate buffer pH 7.4

S.no	Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance at 670 nm
1.	10	0.18
2.	20	0.36
3.	30	0.54
4.	40	0.72
5.	50	0.88

TABLE 10: UV absorbance *curcuma longa* in phosphate buffer pH 7.4

S. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance at 670 nm
1	10	0.18
2	20	0.36
3	30	0.54
4	40	0.72
5	50	0.9

Figure 10: Thin layer chromatography

TABLE 11: Thin layer chromatography

MOBILE PHASE	DETECTOR	SAMPLES	RF VALUE	RESULTS
Toulene: Ethyl acetate: Acetic acid: Ethanol (2.5:7:0.25:0.25)	Iodine Vapour	Quercetin	0.71	Indicates the presence of quercetin
		EMP	0.69	
Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Acetic acid: Ethanol (2.5:7:0.25:0.25)	Iodine Vapour	Quercetin	0.72	Indicates the presence of quercetin
		ECL	0.68	

VIII. CLARITY:**Table 12: Formulation appearance**

SNO	FORMULATION	APPEARANCE
1.	F1	Redish brown colour and turbid
2.	F2	Redish brown colour and turbid
3.	F3	Redish brown colour and turbid

IX. pH:**Table 13: Comparative pH of formulations**

SNO	FORMULATION	pH
1.	F1	6.51± 0.03
2.	F2	6.68± 0.08
3.	F3	6.70± 0.04

X. HOMOGENEITY:**Table 14: Comparative homogeneity of formulation**

SNO	FORMULATION	HOMOGENEITY
1.	F1	Homogeneous
2.	F2	Homogeneous
3.	F3	Homogeneous

XI. SPREADABILITY:**Table 15: Comparative spreadability of formulations**

SNO	FORMULATION	SPREADABILITY (cm)
1	F1	7.00± 0.08
2	F2	6.21± 0.09
3	F3	5.70± 0.06

All values are expressed as mean ± SD, n=3

Table 16: Comparative viscosity of formulations

SNO	FORMULATION	VISCOSITY (cps)
1	F1	2500±60.27
2	F2	3600±136.16
3	F3	4500±56.34

All values are expressed as mean ± SD, n=3

II. TIME FOR DRYING:

Table 17: Comparative drying time of formulations

SNO	FORMULATION	DRYING TIME (min)
1	F1	7min± 44sec
2	F2	6min± 56sec
3	F3	5min± 12sec

All values are expressed as mean ± SD, n=3

Figure 14: Comparative drying time of formulations

Figure 15: Comparative drying time of formulations

XIV. DRUG CONTENT:

Table 18: Comparative content uniformity of formulations

SNO	FORMULATION	CONTENT UNIFORMITY (%)
1	F1	96.42± 0.40
2	F2	95.65± 0.33
3	F3	98.75± 0.27

All values are expressed as mean ± SD, n=3

Figure 16: Comparative content uniformity of formulations

XV. IN VITRO DIFFUSION STUDIES:

Table 19: Comparative *in vitro* diffusion studies of formulations

TIME (hrs)	CUMULATIVE PERCENTAGE OF DRUG RELEASE (%)		
	F1	F2	F3
0	0	0	0
1	38.03±0.13	24.79±0.56	10.23±0.34
2	44.88±0.56	30.47±0.23	15.34±0.46
3	53.26±0.11	39.55±0.14	19.67±0.23
4	58.05±0.23	46.29±0.43	27.57±0.56
5	66.83±0.54	50.33±0.10	34.09±0.26
6	80.75±0.67	56.41±0.22	40.23±0.35
7	96.89±0.12	61.54±0.56	66.56±0.34
8	-	64.44±0.19	86.45±0.31
9	-	69.56±0.21	93.45±0.18
10	-	77.45±0.30	95.45±0.24

Figure 18: Comparative *in vitro* diffusion studies of formulations

XVI. MTT assay:

Table 20: OD VALUE AT 570 nm

S.NO	TESTED SAMPLE CONCENTRATION ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	OD VALUE AT 570 nm (IN TRIPLICATES)			MEAN VALUE (%)
1.	Control	0.498	0.439	0.507	0.481
2.	10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.485	0.454	0.472	0.470
3.	20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.463	0.446	0.455	0.454
4.	40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.436	0.439	0.427	0.434
5.	60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.408	0.421	0.410	0.413
6.	80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.399	0.379	0.404	0.394
7.	100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.353	0.360	0.376	0.363
8.	200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.331	0.333	0.349	0.337
9.	300 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.315	0.325	0.300	0.313
10.	400 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.308	0.288	0.279	0.291
11.	500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.259	0.257	0.216	0.244

Figure 19: OD VALUE OF CONTROL VS F3 AT 570nm

Table 21: Cell viability % of F3

S.NO	TESTED SAMPLE CONCENTRATION (µg/ml)	CELL VIABILITY (%) (IN TRIPLICATES)			MEAN VALUE (%)
1	Control	100	100	100	100
2	10µg/ml	97.3896	103.417	93.0966	97.9676
3	20 µg/ml	92.9719	101.595	89.7436	94.7700
4	40µg/ml	87.5502	100	84.2209	90.5903
5	60µg/ml	81.9277	95.8998	80.8679	86.2317
6	80 µg/ml	80.1205	86.3326	79.6844	82.0458
7	100 µg/ml	70.8835	82.0046	74.1617	75.6832
8	200 µg/ml	66.4659	75.8542	68.8363	70.3854
9	300 µg/ml	63.253	74.0319	59.1716	65.4855
10	400 µg/ml	61.8474	65.6036	55.0296	60.8268
11	500 µg/ml	52.008	58.5421	42.6036	51.0512

XVII. SCRATCH WOUND ASSAY

Figure 21: Control group showing wound at 0 hours

Figure 22: Control group showing wound at 24 hours

Figure 23: F3 Showing wound at 0 hours

Figure 24: F3 Showing wound at 24 hours

Table 22: Densitometry analysis of wound healing assay for control by image J software

TIME	AREA	PERCENT	AREA	PERCENT
0 hr	10652.345	6.65	10676.496	6.45
24 hr	159377.928	99.50	161653.473	97.68

Table 23: Densitometry analysis of wound healing assay for treated by image J software

TIME	AREA	PERCENT	AREA	PERCENT
0 hr	10396.893	11.1	10470.509	9.80
24hr	84337.143	90.56	89203.679	83.54

Table 24: densitometry analysis of wound healing assay by image J software (24 hrs)

SAMPLE DETAILS	PERCENTAGES OF WOUND HEALING (IN DUPLICATES)		MEAN VALUE (%)
Control	99.50	97.68	98.59
Treated with 130µg/ml of F3 sample	90.56	83.54	87.05

Figure 25: % Wound healing of control and F3**CONCLUSION:**

In the current study, three chitosan-based hydrogel formulations elaborated with *Curcuma longa* and *Musa paradisiaca* was developed and evaluated for acute wound healing. One of these (Formulation F3) appeared superior to the other two Formulations (F1 and F2). Improved stability and practicality were shown from the ideal physicochemical properties of F3, such as a suitable pH, excellent homogeneity, acceptable spreadability and enhanced viscosity. In vitro diffusion studies for F3 confirmed a controlled and prolonged drug release profile. Furthermore, cell

migration promoting effect and cytotoxicity results of the scratch wound assay also confirmed that F3 was biocompatible and promoted a higher degree of cell migration implying better wound healing activity. Thus, looking the other way around, formulation F3 become most promising and successful for treating acute wounds.

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